

Watchdog in a Cage: Perspectives on Political Influence on Media Effectiveness in Nigeria

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Abstract

The existence of the media in any society is expected to serve as a check on the excesses of power abusers, which, in turn, should deter all who are prone to such excesses. Over the years, the media in Nigeria have faced several challenges, ranging from weaknesses in their constitutional establishment to the manipulation of journalists within the country. The purpose of this discourse is to situate the ways in which state actors use their political power to cage the press. The paper is anchored on the normative theory of the press. The paper used secondary data to situate the discourse, drawing on distinct cases as examples. The paper posits that the watchdog has been caged: it can barely carry out its responsibilities without governmental or ownership interference, the majority of which has handicapped it. The paper recommends that public officers view the media as state institutions acting in the public interest.

Keywords: free press, media restrictions, democracy and media rights.

Introduction

The media are supposed to be the watchdog, a check on the activities and excesses of the government. Thus, it is the fourth estate of the realm whose responsibility is to watch over the arms of government and to keep the government in check.

Historically, the development of the mass media in Nigeria has an intricate link to politics. This is because, from the establishment of the first newspaper, Iwe Irohin, by Reverend Henry Townsend in 1859 to the stage of media commercialisation in the 1990s, the management and operations of media organisations in Nigeria have been topsy-turvy (Abubakar & Hassan, 2017). Iwe Irohin was nonpartisan at the initial stage, and this protected it from the political interest coupled with a lack of interest in the media operation by the colonial government. Later on, Rev. Henry Townsend dabbled in politics and subjected the paper to political colouration. Expectedly, the paper was punished heavily as it wound off during the Egba political uprising (Oseni, 2000; Oso, 2012; Akinfeleye, 2011) cited in (Chukwu, 2018).

The numerous political interests of newspaper proprietors, which were documented to be mostly self-centred, then forced the colonial government to establish what can be regarded as the first set of media

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regulation; the newspaper ordinance of 1903. This set the stage for media regulation and political influence in Nigeria (Abubakar & Hassan, 2017).

The above decision became the foundation of the government clampdown on the press. Today, however, the media are subject to various controls beyond the government. The commercialisation of the news content is one aspect of caging the media.

On a daily basis, Nigerians are exposed to information, ideas, news, advertisements, messages, and ideologies from different media sources in the course of their daily activities. Citizens have access to all sorts of information from the media, such as radio, television, cable and satellite broadcast, broadband and mobile internet, social networks, smart and ordinary mobile phones, digital audio or video devices, newspapers, magazines, periodicals, and journals.

Interestingly, most societies have spent a great deal of time and resources developing effective systems for using mass media. However, some societies have left the media at the whims of rulers as they come and go. The mass media remain useless unless there is an effective system to harness and use them as instruments of social communication.

Many media experts in Nigeria, Africa, and indeed around the world agree that mass media influence their audiences. However, the direction, nature and extent of this influence remain a source of disagreement. Thompson (1997) noted that the mass media all over the world have established themselves as a new channel - a third channel for political, social, and economic influence - and in many aspects also as an independent power broker. The author believes that the media played a central role in the development of modern institutions. In contrast, Kupe (1999) claims that in the African context, the media have always been peripheral to most people's lives on the continent. But Tettey (2001) argues strongly that the media are among the forces that have shaped and continue to define the establishment of democracy in Africa.

Ekharefo and Omojewve (2019) observe that, over the years, restrictions on the free press have often been viewed through the lens of media laws enacted to check freedom of expression. Nevertheless, the political economy of media management has imposed self-inflicted restrictions that deprive a large majority of the public of the right to express themselves. This paper has argued that the commodification of journalism and its attendant political link to the political class tend to cage the press.

These suggest that the restrictions on the watchdog role of the press concern not just the political space but also the internal structures that affect the capacity of media organisations to perform that role in society. Nevertheless, the focus of this paper is on the political forces that affect the media. Thus, the objective of the paper is to discuss the constitutional framework of the Nigerian press, examine some of the legal restrictions that limit it, and draw on recent cases of abuses of political power that tend to cage the press. To achieve these, the paper uses literature modelling to assess relevant data on the subject of discourse.

Statement of the Problem

The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria confers on the Nigerian press the responsibility of watching the arms of government and holding them accountable. By implication, this means that the press has the constitutional backing to challenge the government and bring it back on track whenever it sways.

However, Agbese (2018) argued that every bony hand owned by men in power loves to reach for the scrawny neck of the press. This unholy ambition has a long history in our country. This indicates that the so-called power of the press is caged or limited by human forces, usually those in “power”, whether in government or in private.

Ordinarily, the constitutional power of the press would serve as a basis for holding the government accountable and promoting the greater good of society. The political economy of media operations tilts in favour of the press acting as agents of those who exercise political and economic power. It is difficult to ascertain how the political institutions and state actors tend to gag the press. This paper draws on relevant case studies on the limitations of the press's effectiveness in carrying out its watchdog function.

Theoretical Framework

A theory often serves as a platform for explaining phenomena. This study uses the Normative theory to explain the subject matter, “The Watchdog in a Cage”.

The normative theories, according to Baran and Davis (2003), postulate that the media can be used by anyone who has an idea to express, but that does not extend to invading private rights or disrupting social structures. It emphasises the freedom of the press and places responsibility on the media practitioners to abide by certain social standards. It opposes media regulation but believes that the press is automatically controlled by community opinion, consumer protest and professional ethics. It calls on the media to be responsible for fostering productive and creative communities, and to do so by prioritising cultural pluralism – by becoming the voice of all the people, not just elite groups or groups that have dominated national, regional or local culture. It also points out that the media, in carrying out their obligations, must adhere to the highest ethical standards.

This theory provides a platform for how the media in any society ought to be managed. While it is obvious that no community has complete press freedom, the standards set by ethics and the Constitution should be upheld by any government in power.

Constitutional Framework for the Nigerian Media

The crucial role of the media can be said to be properly recognised in Nigeria because the nation’s highest law, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended, assigns to the media some specific functions in Chapter 2 titled “Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy”. The chapter spells out the necessary conditions for achieving developed-nation status.

Iredia (2015), however, notes that, unfortunately, as if using the left hand to retrieve what has been given by the right hand, the constitution classifies the chapter as non-justiciable, meaning that the constitution bars the people from legally compelling the government to live up to the high expectations envisaged by the chapter.

Apparently and without doubt, the Nigerian media was established by law and thus regulated by law. Also, chapter 2, section 22, states that “The press, radio, television and other agencies of the mass media shall at all times be free to uphold the fundamental objectives contained in this Chapter and uphold the responsibility and accountability of the Government to the people”.

By law, the Nigerian press is empowered to perform the “watchdog” function, especially in holding the government accountable. The question, however, is “How true or reliable is this power of the media?”

It is noteworthy that the same constitution that provides the media with the power to check the excesses of the government is the same one that confers immunity on certain elements of power in the country. For instance, section 308 makes it impossible for anyone to sue the President or State Governors, whose mandate is to implement public policy.

The following points are stated in the constitution:

- a) No civil or criminal proceedings shall be instituted or continued against a person to whom the section applies during his period of office;
- b) A person to whom the section applies shall not be arrested or imprisoned during that period, either in pursuance of the process of any court or otherwise; and
- c) No process of any court requiring or compelling the appearance of a person to whom the section applies shall be applied for or issued.

The above provisions seem to be a counter to the principle that the government shall be held accountable. So, if the constitution says the press is charged with the responsibility of holding the government accountable, and it still protects the same government officials from being prosecuted while in office, of what use is the power?

Meanwhile, Chukwu (2018) observes that in Nigeria, there is no clear-cut or explicit constitutional framework for freedom of information and the effective practice of journalism. Rather, so many laws are made to create impediments on the latter: laws like the Official Secret Act, Censorship laws and others. The press in Nigeria draws its power to source for information ostensibly from the amorphous Section 39, which guaranteed for freedom of expression for all citizens, and Section 22 which provides for the duties of the mass media to the Nigerian society thus: “The press, radio, television and other agencies of the mass media shall at all times be free to uphold the fundamental objectives contained in this chapter and uphold the responsibility and accountability of the Government to the people”.

A closer look, according to Chukwu's submission, draws attention to the fact that freedom of the press has no legal backing. Sections 22 and 39 only make provisions for media ownership and the

responsibilities of the media. One can reasonably argue that, from the foregoing, the freedom of the press is a mere mirage in Nigeria.

However, Osinbajo and Fogan (1991,p.8) provided the right answer to what constitutes freedom of the press, thus: “freedom of the press is, really, freedom under the law”. They add that “since the press finds its ultimate freedom and protection in law, it must also conform to the boundaries established by law. Even though a few voices have urged absolute press freedom”. Invariably, the constitution's provision for freedom of expression guarantees press freedom, although it is not explicitly spelt out.

Aturu (2010) draws attention to the fact that the empowerment of media owners should not be mistaken for that of the media. The opinion is that seeking a provision for freedom in the constitution is indirectly an attempt to be pampered. Those who may think so may have a change of heart upon seeing how some other countries have handled the subject.

Nigeria is not yet a free and open society despite the availability of diverse viewpoints flowing from a remarkable abundance of press organisations in the country. However, several press organisations in Nigeria lack complete freedom due to censorship, multiple power centres and volatile political institutions (Agbaje, 1992). Despite the proliferation of press organisations, constitutional provisions for press freedom have not been fully enforced.

It is equally a weak point to assume that the media are fully empowered to function because section 39 (2) of the constitution provides that—**every person shall be entitled to own, establish and operate any medium for the dissemination of information, ideas and opinions**. A proper scrutiny of the provision reveals that it merely protects the interests of owners, not those of media professionals, who are the real operatives tasked with policing the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy enshrined in Chapter 2 of the Constitution (Iredia, 2015).

The above submission indicates that the constitution's provision on media ownership is favourable only to media owners; it is not a freedom pass for the media. It is pertinent to reemphasise here that it is he who plays the piper who dictates the tune. So, whether the constitution provides a platform for individuals to own media outlets is not enough to give those who function on such a platform the audacity to dictate how things ought to happen.

Beyond constitutional limitations, there are laws that hinder the press's ability to effectively monitor society. While some of the laws are designed to guarantee a sane society, their application to the press tends to gag it and leave it helpless.

According to Ekhareafu and Omojewve (2019), in exercising their rights within the realm of press freedom, many journalists have been harassed and imprisoned, with certain national laws used as a basis for such actions. Thus, the provisions of the National Security Act, the Official Secrets Act, sedition, treason, and contempt of court have always been seen as restrictive laws aimed at gagging the press. Nevertheless, there is a growing trend that appears restrictive and self-inflicted, a pull against press freedom and the market-driven model of mass media. The market-driven model is anchored on the political economy of the mass media.

This is why Agbese (2018) quoted an old saying that “Every bony hand owned by men in power loves to reach for the scrawny neck of the press. This unholy ambition has a long history in our country” he echoes the concern of Tony Momoh, thus;

A few years down the road, Prince Tony Momoh, editor, media manager, columnist, lawyer and former minister of information, compiled a disturbing evidence of official hostility towards the Nigerian press. According to him, there had been 51 anti-press laws in the land since 1917, as at the time he compiled them. I am sure the number must have since inched up, seeing as I am not aware of the emergence of a new generation of press lovers in the corridors of power in our country. If you look at each of those laws as a rope in search of an editor’s neck, you would have a fairly good idea of what the press has been up against.

The Nigerian press has been under “close supervision” by the powers that be. Regardless of the provisions of the law and the existence of the Freedom of Information Bill, the liberty of the press is still being toyed with.

Elite capture of the press-driven public sphere portends danger for democracy as it creates multiple voices that produce different versions of various class interests and exclude the interests of the poor. The economic imperatives behind the operations of many press organisations tend to trump their public service role (Tettey, 2008). This situation introduces a dilemma in understanding the press's contributions to the development of Nigerian democracy. Painfully, freedom of expression and human rights are in a state of siege in Nigeria, with journalists and their family members routinely arrested, tortured and detained. The Nigerian situation is among the worst cases of press repression in the world (Akinwale, 2010).

Basically, the press in Nigeria seems to have no standing, either serving as a tool in the hands of the mighty or as a watchdog without teeth. Ojo (2006) observed that the government used Decree 60 to establish the Nigerian Press Council (NPC) in 1999 and charged it with enforcing professional ethics. Immediately, the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ) and the Newspaper Proprietors Association of Nigeria (NPAN) rejected the creation of the Press Council because the decree contained provisions perceived as inimical to the operation of a free press. The NPC was empowered to accredit and register journalists. In applying for registration, publishers were expected to submit their mission statements and objectives and could be denied registration if their objectives failed to satisfy the NPC. The penalties for operating without meeting the Council’s standard were a fine of N250,000 (\$2,500) or three years’ imprisonment.

Asemah (2011) provides some limitations to the effectiveness/freedom of the press in Nigeria. These limitations include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Legal pressure: Chigbo (2007) observes that section 39 subsection 3 validates and justifies any law made for the purpose of preventing disclosure of information received in strict

confidence while serving the government.

The above points to the fact that press freedom is a mirage. In other words, the press is still in a cage, and how can the watchdog truly watch when it is caged? Thus, its powers are reduced to mere observation without input.

- Economic and political pressure: Where ownership is concerned, the media cannot publish anything that does not go well with the owner of its affiliates. The domination of the media by the political class makes it susceptible to the vagaries of political interests and considerations.
- Secrecy. Even with the passage of the Freedom of Information Act, access to public information remains an issue. The Conference of Civil Society Organisations, Edo State Chapter, had alleged through their Public Relations Officer in a sensitisation seminar on the Freedom of Information Act, organised by the National Orientation Agency in April 2020, that the body had written over 18 letters requesting information on government projects and programmes but turned down on the grounds that the act has not been domesticated in the state.
- Direct censorship and force: In June 2014, the Nigerian soldiers ceased print copies of *The Nation*, *Punch*, *Daily Trust*, and *Leadership* newspapers on the grounds that they compromised national security. In the same vein, AIT was shut down by the National Broadcasting Commission from 6th to 9th June over the station's programme, *Kaakaaki Social*, which reviews social media comments on developments in society.

Watchdog in a Cage: Recent Cases of Limitation on the Press Function

Bruns (2008) maintains that critical independence, democratic constructiveness and commercial viability are the cardinal principles of press organisation. Governments have been using licenses and censorship to control the power of mass media and curtail its immense contribution and defence of fundamental human rights. As a fourth estate, the press holds the executive, legislature, and judiciary accountable to the public by exercising the functions of a watchdog and a surveillance role.

Bruns' opinion is that the media do not enjoy freedom, as things that characterise their existence are not actualised.

As noted earlier, the June 6th-9th closure of AIT, on the flimsy excuse of national security and the rebroadcast of social media content, raises questions about the motive behind the closure. Social media is a public space where netizens comment on issues in society. The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) argued that the rebroadcast of social media content violates the NBC code. Omilana (2019), quoting the reaction of the former Vice President, Atiku Abubakar, observes that "If, at this time, we stand by as the press loses its independence, there will be little to differentiate us from a dictatorship." (m.guardian.ng on 9th June, 2019).

The closure of the renowned broadcast outfit in Nigeria was condemned by the Nigerian Union of Journalists and many Nigerians. The closure could be interpreted as victimising the broadcast medium, as the AIT had been a strong opposition to the government of the day. One then wonders

whether the press truly still has a voice. The watchdog is being put in a cage where its teeth are harmless, and its barking has no effect.

In the same year, precisely 3rd August, 2019, the publisher of Sahara Reporters, Omoyele Sowore, was arrested by the men of the Directorate of State Security on treason charges for calling for a revolution. The arrest generated global reaction. The journalist and publisher had launched a peaceful Revolution Now protest to fight for the rights of the average Nigerian, against abuse of office by political leaders and unconstitutional operations by the same. He was granted bail, but the Department of State Security (DSS) rearrested him within the premises of the court.

In another case, Sahara Reporters reported the fraudulent removal of Gbenga Aruleba, presenter of Focus Nigeria on AIT, over what the government termed a critical stance against it. According to the report:

Investigations by Sahara Reporters reveal that the chairman of DAAR Group, Mr Raymond Aleogho Dokpesi, decided to remove a popular presenter of the current affairs TV program, “Focus Nigeria,” from the air following pressures from the Umaru Yar’adua regime. Sources within the government, as well as a confidant of the AIT owner, told our correspondents that Mr Dokpesi sacrificed the integrity of the program, presented by Gbenga Aruleba, to stave off the government’s threat to press corruption charges against him and to ruin his businesses. Early this week, Dokpesi ordered Aruleba replaced with another presenter after the AIT owner told members of the NUJ that Aruleba’s life was in danger from overzealous security agents in Abuja. Saharareporters gathered that Dokpesi’s action came after he was summoned by the National Security Adviser (NSA), “who expressed Yar’adua’s displeasure with the program”, which is aired as a morning show Monday to Friday. The NSA warned Dokpesi that Aruleba’s manner of hosting the program, which often featured critical segments on Yar’adua’s usurper-government, “threatens the security of the nation.” According to a source familiar with the interaction, the NSA “ordered Dokpesi to do something to curtail the excesses of Mr Aruleba.”

The press is at the mercy of lawmakers when it should be checking their excesses. However, the powers that be are in total control of the press. The Nigerian press has obviously lost its position as the Fourth Estate of the Realm.

The Nigerian Press Council Bill 2018 was one such way through which the government could have silenced or critically crippled the power of the press, or even its entire existence. Vanguard (www.vanguardngr.com, 24/07/2018) reports that publishers, editors, the Nigerian Union of Journalists, and other media stakeholders, at a public hearing in Abuja, rejected the bill after speaking unanimously against it.

In the statement presented by the Chairman, Newspapers Proprietors’ Association of Nigeria (NPAN), on behalf of media stakeholders, in part, read:

“Consequent upon the above, the meeting observed and resolved as follows: “The proposed bill is unconstitutional as it runs against the principles and tenets of the rule of law and is actually sub-judice, given that a case on the subject matter is still pending in the highest court of the land—the

Supreme Court— in view of which the bill should not have been drafted in the first instance. “That the bill is, for all intents and purposes, draconian and anti-press freedom, being an amalgamation of the obnoxious Public Officers (Protection Against False Accusation) Decree No. 4 of 1984 and Newspapers Registration Decree 43 of 1993, both vestiges of the dark days of military rule and, therefore, incurably and irreparably bad, being also inconsistent with values of our democratic society.”

There are other cases of government infringement of the press's right to cover events and report issues. Ekhareafo (2020) noted a case of the brutal handling of a female reporter by aides to Governor Nasir El Rufai in May 2018 over what they perceived as negative reporting on the government. The Directorate of State Security arrested Darah Ebi in 2016, locked him up in their detention cell for two years without charge on the grounds that he was privy to a plot by the Niger Delta militants to bomb oil facilities. In Edo State, the Governor, Godwin Obaseki, ordered the suspension of two current affairs programmes on the grounds that they are used to attack his government.

In conclusion, one wonders why the powers that be are waging war against the media. Apparently, efforts are still on towards crippling the power of the press (which is not even there in the first place) and mitigating the effectiveness of the same.

Recommendations

The paper makes the following recommendations to strengthen the media for optimum performance.

1. State security officials should respect the right of media men to report issues. When there are infractions against the state, there is a need for such officials to allow the law courts to do their job.
2. Nigeria needs to adopt the principles of open government. This will help reduce the incidence of government officials taking adversarial measures against the press for reporting what they term official security.
3. The courts need to hasten judgments in the many cases in the states where the state governments claim the states need to domesticate the Freedom of Information Act before it can be justiciable.

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